

ZIGMA MEDICARE INDIA (OPC) PRIVATE LIMITED

No.26 A, Balaji Nagar, East Zone, Coimbatore – 641048

In Association with .,

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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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Dynamic Dashboard For Airbnb Data Analysis Using Streamlit.

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ABSTRACT :

This project presents a dynamic dashboard for Airbnb data analysis, leveraging the Streamlit framework to provide an interactive and user-friendly platform for exploring insights from Airbnb datasets. The dashboard enables users to uncover trends in pricing, availability, and customer preferences across different regions and time periods. It features customizable visualizations, advanced filtering options, and real-time data interactivity, empowering users to perform detailed exploratory data analysis without extensive programming knowledge. The integration of data preprocessing, machine learning predictions, and geospatial mapping enhances the decision-making process for hosts, travelers, and industry stakeholders. This tool demonstrates the potential of Streamlit for building powerful, scalable, and accessible applications in the domain of data analytics.

Keywords: Airbnb Analytics, Streamlit Dashboard, Short-term Rental Trends, Data Visualization, Pricing Analysis, Customer Insights, Geographic Distribution, Machine Learning in Hospitality, Travel and Tourism Data, Interactive Data Exploration, Seasonal Demand Analysis, Real Estate Market Insights

1. INTRODUCTION :

Airbnb has revolutionized the hospitality industry, offering a platform for unique accommodations worldwide. With its growing popularity, analyzing Airbnb data has become essential for understanding market trends, customer behavior, and optimizing decision-making for hosts, travelers, and policymakers. However, the large volume and complexity of this data demand advanced tools that make analysis accessible and intuitive for both technical and non-technical users. This project introduces a dynamic dashboard powered by Streamlit, an open-source framework for building interactive web applications in Python. The dashboard provides an intuitive interface for visualizing and analyzing Airbnb data, enabling users to explore key metrics such as pricing trends, availability patterns, and customer preferences across regions and timeframes. Through interactive visualizations, customizable filters, and data-driven insights, the platform simplifies the process of exploratory data analysis, making it accessible to a wide audience.

2. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION :

The rapid growth of Airbnb as a global platform has generated vast amounts of data, including listings, reviews, pricing, and availability. While this data holds significant potential for uncovering insights into market trends and customer preferences, several challenges impede effective utilization:

2.1 Data Volume and Complexity: The sheer size and heterogeneity of Airbnb datasets make it challenging to analyze them effectively, especially for users without advanced technical expertise.

2.2 Lack of Accessibility: Many traditional data analysis tools require coding skills or extensive training, limiting access for non-technical stakeholders such as hosts, travelers, and policymakers.

2.3 Fragmented Insights: Insights often remain siloed due to the lack of integrated platforms for analyzing multiple aspects such as pricing trends, location dynamics, and customer reviews.

2.4 Static Reporting: Conventional dashboards often lack interactivity and real-time customization, reducing their effectiveness for exploratory data analysis and decision-making.

2.5 Actionable Insights: Translating raw data into actionable insights remains a challenge for many users, particularly when identifying specific patterns or trends relevant to their needs.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Use Python libraries like Pandas, Matplotlib, and Seaborn to understand data distributions, detect anomalies, and identify significant trends.

Perform correlation analysis to assess relationships between variables (e.g., price vs. location).

3.1 Frontend Design: Develop an intuitive and responsive user interface for displaying visualizations and interactive widgets.

3.2 Visualization: Incorporate libraries such as Plotly and Altair to create dynamic charts, heatmaps, and scatter plots.

3.3 Geospatial Mapping: Integrate geospatial libraries (e.g., Folium or Pydeck) to visualize geographic trends and spatial relationships.

3.4 Interactivity: Add features like sliders, dropdowns, and search bars to allow users to filter and customize views.

Fig (1) : AirBnb-Analysis

4. METHOD OF COMPARISON :

Compare metrics such as average response time, accuracy of insights, and percentage of tasks successfully completed using each tool. Use statistical analysis to validate differences and identify significant advantages of the Streamlit dashboard.

Summarize the findings, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of the Streamlit dashboard compared to traditional tools. Focus on aspects where Streamlit excels, such as interactivity, accessibility, and the ability to provide deeper insights.

This structured comparison ensures that the dashboard's value proposition is clearly demonstrated, guiding further enhancements and adoption.

Fig (2) : Air-Bnb Analysis in Map View

5. CONCLUSION :

The development of the dynamic dashboard for Airbnb data analysis using Streamlit highlights the transformative potential of interactive and user-friendly tools in data exploration and decision-making. By addressing challenges such as data complexity, accessibility, and the

need for actionable insights, the dashboard bridges the gap between raw data and informed decision-making for a diverse audience, including hosts, travelers, and industry analysts.

The comparison with traditional methods and tools demonstrates that the Streamlit-powered dashboard excels in key areas such as usability, interactivity, and real-time customization. Its integration of advanced features like geospatial mapping, dynamic visualizations, and predictive analytics enhances the depth and quality of insights, empowering users to uncover trends and make data-driven decisions efficiently.

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